

Research

Study on the Clinical Effects of Different Surgical Treatments for Inguinal Hernia

Sanjay Chaudhary^{1*}

¹Department of General Surgery, Janaki Medical College and Teaching Hospital, Nepal

Abstract: Objective: To discuss the clinical effects of different surgical treatments for inguinal hernia.

Methods: Select 120 patients with inguinal hernia treated in Janaki Medical College and Teaching Hospital, Janakpur Nepal from May 2023 to May 2024, and divide them into two groups according to the random number method, 60 cases in each group, treated with tension-free hernia repair surgery. The experimental group was the experimental group, and the control group was treated with traditional hernia repair surgery. The hospitalization time, surgical blood loss, operation time, complication rate, quality of life, the effect of only come, pain score, etc. were compared between the two groups.

Results: In the experimental group, the amount of bleeding during operation was 7.05 ± 2.48 mL, the length of hospital stay was 5.05 ± 0.45 d, the incision length was 1.23 ± 0.35 cm, the operation time was 10.17 ± 1.52 min, the complication rate was 1.67%, and the total effective rate was 95.00%. Total quality of life score 95.32 ± 1.27 , pain score 2.63 ± 0.05 , anxiety score 32.87 ± 1.59 , depression score 33.62 ± 1.78 , Were better than those in the control group 16.48 ± 3.36 mL, 10.15 ± 0.18 d, 4.09 ± 0.95 cm, 15.18 ± 1.52 min, 18.33%, 85.00%, 82.52 ± 1.77 , 4.93 ± 0.07 , 45.23 ± 1.78 , 46.58 ± 1.77 . The difference was significant ($P < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The use of tension-free hernia repair surgery in patients with inguinal hernia can relieve pain, reduce blood loss during surgery, shorten hospital stay, improve treatment effect, improve quality of life, and reduce the incidence of complications.

Keywords: tension-free hernia repair surgery; traditional hernia repair surgery; inguinal hernia

*Corresponding Author: Sanjay Chaudhary, Department of general surgery, Janaki medical college and teaching hospital, Nepal

Accepted: 16 June, 2024; **Published:** 26 June, 2024

How to cite this article: Sanjay Chaudhary (2024). Study on the Clinical Effects of Different Surgical Treatments for Inguinal Hernia. North American Academic Research, 7(6), 50-54. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12572806>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) is fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Inguinal hernia is a common clinical disease, which can be divided into two forms: indirect hernia and direct hernia. The incidence of indirect hernia is higher [1]. After the onset of the disease, patients will experience increased intra-abdominal pressure and decreased abdominal muscle strength, which will also affect daily life and reduce the patient's quality of life [2]. Inguinal hernia is a disease caused by an organ or tissue in the inguinal area leaving its normal position, resulting in a weak point or defect in the abdomen [3]. Surgery is generally used in treatment, but patients need to bear great pain during the treatment process. The types of surgery mainly include traditional hernia repair surgery,

preperitoneal repair surgery, laparoscopic hernia repair surgery, tension-free hernia repair surgery, etc. Different types of surgery have different effects after treatment, and there are also differences in related indications after surgery [4]. In this article, 120 patients with inguinal hernia from May 2023 to May 2024 were selected for research, and the specific report is as follows.

Research Methodology

120 patients with inguinal hernia were selected, including the experimental group: the male-female ratio was 1:1, and the average age was 51.88 ± 1.76 years old. The control group: the male-female ratio was 7:5, and the average age was 50.99 ± 1.82 years old. The general data of the two groups of patients were slightly different ($P > 0.05$) and can be compared. Inclusion criteria: ① The patient signed the informed consent form; ② The patient was diagnosed with inguinal hernia. Exclusion criteria: ① The patient had an allergic constitution; ② The patient had systemic diseases. This study was approved by the hospital ethics committee.

In the control group, conventional repair surgery was used. The patients were given general anesthesia. An incision was made at the location of the hernia lesion. The inguinal hernia was removed by high ligation. Then the spermatic cord or round ligament of the uterus was lifted, and the conjoined tendon, the oblique lower edge of the intra-abdominal muscles, and the skin were sutured layer by layer. In the experimental group, tension-free hernia repair surgery was used. General anesthesia was used during the operation. An incision was made about 0.5 cm above the inguinal ligament. The incision needed to reach the tubercle of the pubic bone, which was about 3 to 5 cm. The superficial fascia of the patient was cut, the oblique aponeurosis of the abdomen was cut, and blunt separation was performed layer by layer to expose the inguinal ligament, the spermatic cord was freed and abdominalized, the hernia sac was freed to a high position, and the hernia sac was closed at the proximal end. A preperitoneal space was established, and a patch was placed in the preperitoneal space and fixed to the surrounding area. A flat patch was added behind the spermatic cord, and then the incision was sutured.

The intraoperative blood loss, incision length, hospital stay, operation time, anxiety score, depression score, complication rate, treatment effect, quality of life score, and pain score before and after treatment were observed in the two groups.

Efficacy judgment criteria: ① Significant effect. After treatment, the patient's lumps completely disappeared, and the abdominal pain disappeared, and there was no recurrence within 3 months. ② Effective. After treatment, the patient's lumps partially disappeared and shrank, and the abdominal pain was relieved, and occasional recurrence occurred within 3 months. ③ Ineffective. After treatment, the patient's lumps did not disappear or shrink, and the abdominal pain did not ease, and the disease always recurred within 3 months.

SPSS 29.0 software was used to analyze the measurement data $\bar{x} \pm s$ using t test; the enumeration data % was analyzed using χ^2 test, and $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

Comparison of intraoperative blood loss, incision length, hospitalization and operation time between the two groups
Comparison of intraoperative blood loss, incision length, hospitalization time and operation time between the two groups the experimental group had lower intraoperative blood loss, shorter hospitalization time, shorter incision length and shorter operation time, and the difference between the two groups was significant ($P < 0.05$). See Table 1.

Table 1 Comparison of intraoperative blood loss, incision length, hospital stay and operation time between the two groups ($\bar{x} \pm s$)

Group	Number of cases	Incision length (cm)	Intraoperative blood loss (mL)	Length of hospital stay (d)	Operation time (min)
Experiment group	60	1.23 ± 0.35	7.05 ± 2.48	5.05 ± 0.45	10.17 ± 1.52

Control group	60	4.09±0.95	16.48±3.36	10.15±0.18	15.18±1.52
t		21.881	17.491	81.509	18.053
P		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

The incidence of complications in the experimental group was lower ($P < 0.05$). See Table 2.

Table 2 Comparison of complication rates between the two groups [n (%)]

Group	Number of cases	Scrotal abscess	Incision infection	Recurrent hernia	Complication rate
Experiment group	60	1 (1.67)	0 (0.00)	0 (0.00)	1 (1.67)
Control group	60	3 (5.00)	5 (8.33)	3 (5.00)	11 (18.33)
t					13.624
P					0.000

Comparison of the treatment effects between the two groups showed that the total effective rate of the experimental group was higher ($P < 0.05$). See Table 3.

Table 3 Comparison of treatment effects between the two groups [n (%)]

Group	Number of cases	Significant effect	efficient	invalid	Total Effectiveness
Experiment group	60	48 (80.00)	9 (15.00)	3 (5.00)	57 (95.00)
Control group	60	33 (55.00)	18 (30.00)	9 (15.00)	51 (85.00)
t					8.182
P					0.004

The quality of life scores of the two groups were compared, and the experimental group was better ($P < 0.05$). See Table 4.

Table 4 Comparison of quality of life scores between the two groups (x±s)

Group	Number of cases	Physical function	Social function	Psychological function	Emotional function	Role function	Overall quality of life score
Experiment group	60	92.36±1.85	91.33±1.75	90.36±1.55	92.18±1.66	93.32±1.87	95.32±1.27
Control group	60	81.32±1.75	80.62±1.55	81.29±1.37	82.51±1.66	83.52±1.67	82.52±1.77
t		33.581	35.487	33.962	31.906	30.278	45.513
P		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Comparison of pain scores between the two groups before and after treatment showed that the pain score in the experimental group was lower ($P < 0.05$). Comparison of anxiety and depression scores between the two groups showed that the experimental group had better scores ($P < 0.05$).

Discussion

Inguinal hernia is a common surgical disease with a high incidence in children and the elderly [5]. In most children, due to congenital incomplete development of the abdominal wall muscles, the hernia will recover automatically as they grow older [6]. However, some children cannot recover on their own and need surgery, otherwise the hernia will be incarcerated, causing symptoms such as high fever, vomiting, nausea, and even threatening the life of the child [7-9]. In the elderly, due to their old age, the abdominal muscles atrophy and the abdominal wall gradually thins. When straining to defecate or cough, the abdominal pressure increases, leading to hernia [10-14]. Traditional hernia repair surgery is

generally used in treatment, but it is easy to cause damage to the ilioinguinal and peripheral nerves during treatment, and it will also damage the structure of the groin. In addition, the operation time is relatively long, the incidence of postoperative complications is high, and the patient's physical recovery is slow after the operation, and it takes a long time to get out of bed. There is also a high recurrence rate, which has a great impact on the patient's daily life [15-18]. Tension-free hernia repair surgery uses artificial biomaterial patches to strengthen the posterior wall of the inguinal canal, which is beneficial to the patient's physical recovery and can also avoid damage to the ilioinguinal and peripheral nerves. The incidence of complications after surgery is low [19]. After the repair, the patient's surgical site is in a tension-free state, which is conducive to wound healing.

This article selected 120 patients with inguinal hernia. The treatment effect of patients using traditional hernia repair surgery (85.00%) was lower than that of patients using tension-free hernia repair surgery (95.00%). In the study by Xiao Yunlong et al. [15], the treatment efficacy of patients using tension-free hernia repair surgery (97.22%) was higher than that of patients using conventional hernia repair surgery (86.11%), which is similar to the results of this study.

Patients treated with tension-free hernia repair surgery had lower pain levels, shorter incision lengths, less bleeding during surgery, and shorter surgery times. This shows that tension-free hernia repair surgery is simple to operate and has strong surgical safety. Patients treated with tension-free hernia repair surgery have a lower incidence of complications such as incision infection, scrotal abscess, and recurrent hernia, a shorter hospital stay, a higher quality of life, and lower anxiety and depression scores.

Conclusion

Compared with traditional hernia repair surgery, the use of tension-free hernia repair surgery has a lower incidence of postoperative infection events, allows patients to get out of bed and move around early after surgery, and recovers faster, improving the quality of life of patients. Therefore, tension-free hernia repair surgery is widely used and can also be used in elderly patients with poor physical fitness and younger children. In summary, the use of tension-free hernia repair surgery in patients with inguinal hernia can relieve pain, reduce intraoperative bleeding, shorten hospital stay, improve treatment effects, improve quality of life, and reduce the incidence of complications.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Hu Yang. Clinical efficacy analysis of different tension-free hernioplasty methods in the treatment of inguinal hernia[J]. Chinese Community Physician, 2020, 36(15):73+75.
2. Li Diangang. Comparative study on the efficacy of different tension-free hernioplasty methods in the treatment of inguinal hernia[J]. Psychological Monthly, 2020, 15(13):206.
3. Liu Ning, Chen Xiangyun, Wang Lei, et al. Clinical analysis of two different surgical methods for the treatment of inguinal cryptorchidism[J]. Journal of Medical Forum, 2020, 41(4):66-69.
4. Li Xinguo. Comparison of clinical efficacy and recurrence of different tension-free hernioplasty methods in the treatment of inguinal hernia[J]. Electronic Journal of Clinical Medical Literature, 2020, 7(8):75-76.
5. Ahmet Sürek, Mehmet Abdussamet Bozkurt, Sina Ferahman, et al. Laparoscopic Total Extraperitoneal Inguinal Hernia Repair Under Epidural

6. Anesthesia Versus General Anesthesia[J]. *Surgical Laparoscopy, Endoscopy & Percutaneous Techniques*, 2020, 30(5):471-475.
7. Li Hui. Clinical efficacy of different methods of tension-free hernia repair in the treatment of inguinal hernia[J]. *World Latest Medical Information Abstracts*, 2019, 19(A3):76-77.
8. Li Ruizhong, Gui Jianxing. Comparative study on the clinical effects of different surgical treatment methods for inguinal hernia[J]. *World Latest Medical Information Abstracts*, 2019, 19(75):80-81.
9. Dawa, Mao Wei. Comparison of clinical effects of different surgical treatment methods for inguinal hernia patients in plateau areas[J]. *World Latest Medical Information Abstracts*, 2019, 19(68):105+107.
10. Han Xin. Analysis of the efficacy of different tension-free hernioplasty in the treatment of inguinal hernia[J]. *China Medical Guide*, 2019, 17(19): 56.
11. Li Jianhua. Analysis of the clinical efficacy of different tension-free hernioplasty in the treatment of inguinal hernia[J]. *World Latest Medical Information Abstracts*, 2019, 19(39): 82+84.
12. Shahin Hajibandeh, Shahab Hajibandeh, Shahd Mobarak, et al. Meta-Analysis of Spinal Anesthesia Versus General Anesthesia
13. During Laparoscopic Total Extraperitoneal Repair of Inguinal Hernia[J]. *Surgical Laparoscopy, Endoscopy & Percutaneous Techniques*, 2020, 30(4): 371-380.
14. Wang Zhiliang. Analysis of the clinical efficacy of different tension-free hernioplasty methods in the treatment of inguinal hernia[J]. *Smart Health*, 2019, 5(11): 123-124+126.
15. Wu Yang. Analysis of the clinical efficacy of different tension-free hernioplasty methods in the treatment of inguinal hernia[J]. *Chinese and Foreign Medical Treatment*, 2019, 38(9): 61-63.
16. Xu Zefeng. Comparison of clinical effects of different surgical treatment methods in the treatment of 100 patients with inguinal hernia[J]. *Contemporary Medicine*, 2018, 24(33): 154-156.
17. Xiao Yunlong, Tang Jinsong. Comparative study on the clinical effects of different surgical treatment methods in the treatment of inguinal hernia[J]. *Systems Medicine*, 2018, 3(24): 111-113.
18. Benedetto Ielpo, Yolanda Quijano, Emilio Vicente, et al. Laparoscopic Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) Inguinal Hernia Repair Using Fibrin

